

A CONTEMPORARY APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF LOCALLY ADVANCED BREAST CANCER

Ahmedov Furqat Ramatovich

TTA Urganch branch

Cost : Various literature comments seeing exit with BS during hurt patients for oncological of help effect , treatment-diagnosis approach enough effect fencer and potential efficient methods seeing released One series researchers by to the conducted IGX tests based on , many of molecular BS subtypes features and illness indicators , spread and to meet level and clinical stages main differences , biological features of metastasis location and level , therapeutic approaches about information to get succeeded divided . of KS subtypes molecular class formation , as well as har one the patient for individually of the disease result about information get point of view in terms of useful to be can Own in turn , this is the optimal therapeutic approach to create help will give . Genomics through received achievements in BS cases diagnosis approach to improve and healer therapy work exit , this category to patients individualized approach to choose help will give .

Material and methods: Research RIO and RIATM Tashkent city in the branch treated local spread out breast diaper cancer with 115 patients the patient introduced. Patients two to the group divided by : main group (from NAXT then IGX results changed 66 patients) and control group (from NAXT then IGX status unchanged 49 patients).

Result: Basic in the group average common viability indicator 3 years organize did , control 2.5 years in the group . Main in the group without relapse to live level is also high is an average of 2 years , control in the group and 1.5 years .

Conclusion: So , different BS aspects , including genetic , molecular and cell features to learn complex approach , as well as oncology within interdisciplinary

the experience combine to us this category patients for treatment efficiency increase and forecast improve the way opens .